

Water flux and hydrological processes quantification in agricultural fields under different tillage and irrigation systems using water stable isotopes

Canet-Martí, A.^{1*}, Morales-Santos, A.², Nolz, R.², Langergraber, G.¹, Stumpp, C.²

¹ University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna (BOKU), Institute for Sanitary Engineering and Water pollution Control (SIG), Muthgasse 18, 1190 Wien, Austria

² University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna (BOKU), Institute for Soil Physics and Rural Water Management (SoPhy), Muthgasse 18, 1190 Wien, Austria

*e-mail: alba.canet@boku.ac.at

In order to achieve sustainable agriculture, it is necessary to assess the impacts that management practices may have on the hydrological processes at the catchment level. The quantification of soil water fluxes would provide valuable information for understanding changes in hydrological processes. However, it is still difficult to directly quantify water fluxes in the soil which has been mainly indirectly quantified by complex numerical modelling methods. The aim of our study was to quantify average water fluxes in agricultural fields using a space for time concept, first employing oxygen and hydrogen isotope ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$) measurements of soil pores to identify a period in soil depth profiles, and then volumetric water content to quantify soil water flux during that period, considered as mobile water. A water balance approach is used for quantifying the evapotranspiration. The bulk effect of management practices on water fluxes are analyzed across four irrigation systems (drip irrigation (DI), sprinkler irrigation (SI), hose reel boom irrigation with nozzles (BI), and no irrigation (NI)), and four tillage variants (conventional tillage (CT), reduced tillage (RT), minimal tillage (MT) and no tillage (NT)). Tracing the minimum in the pore water stable isotope profiles we observed a gradual change in water flow velocity on the order $\text{CT} > \text{RT} \approx \text{MT} > \text{NT}$. Considering both water content and differences in water flow velocities resulted in water fluxes ranging from 3.6 to 8.2 mm/month. Differences in soil mobile water were less pronounced in irrigation systems than in tillage variants, which followed an upward trend in mobile water as tillage intensity decreased (Fig 1). The resulting evapotranspiration within tillage and irrigation variants decreased in the order $\text{CT} > \text{RT} > \text{MT} > \text{NT}$, and $\text{SI} > \text{BI} > \text{DI} > \text{NI}$ (Fig 1). Irrigation water showed to contribute mostly to evapotranspiration, and drip irrigation showed the lowest evapotranspiration losses among irrigation systems. This study demonstrated that water stable isotopes can be used as indicators and are a promising method to quantify water fluxes in agricultural fields with great potential for evaluating management practices.

Fig. 1: Mean values of evapotranspiration and mobile soil water calculated for a period of six months for tillage variants and irrigation systems, in mm. The lines within the bars represent the standard deviation.